

SEED DIVERSITY FAIR JHARKHAND

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Compiled and submitted By

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Public Advocacy Initiatives for Rights and Values in India (PAIRVI)

Under

FAO (ITPGR) BSF-IV Cycle Project for India on Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

Background

The FAO funded project on “Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population”. This innovative project is implemented by PAIRVI, New Delhi in five states including JHARKHAND. The aim of the project is to enhance the availability and onfarm conservation of resilient varieties of pulses (traditional varieties, varieties procured from gene banks as well as under-utilized species of pulses) and oil seeds for cultivation during the rice fallow season. The project decided to conduct community seeds fair on 31st December 2022 at its project location Jharkhand (Five villages participated: Tulsitar, Koyadah, Behroki, Magnasar, Bhalsuniya) State.

Strategies

Bihar team of PAIRVI prepared the following strategies for conducting the one day “Community Seed Fair” successfully.

1. Effective implementation designed for achieving the effective and meaningful seed fair
 - a. Farming community and volunteers at project location played a key role. The project volunteers and farming community members were oriented on how to mobilize the farmers including women during this challenging time of COVID19.
 - b. A dedicated team / Seed Fair Committee (SFC) consists of community members led by State Coordinator, conducted the fair.
 - c. Team concentrated to the project villages and adjacent area of the project location only. The local officials from Panchayat Raj Institutions (PRIs) and agriculture department also were invited.
 - d. Planned to build low-cost stalls, main entrance gate and stage for cultural events (tents / pandal) to attract the tribal and other participants.
 - e. Display of IEC materials for creating awareness on diversified pulse cultivation and COVID19 among the farmers.
 - f. The responsible persons of team were taking care of registration, photography/ video, foods, logistics, sanitization, reporting etc.
2. The rejuvenate project team to achieving the following targeta. Permission from administration:
 - b. Selection of fair location: Open ground of bhalsuniya field
 - c. Purchasing of clay pots: For display
 - d. Finalization of farmers for display at stalls: Both men and women
 - e. Selection of Vendors / suppliers: Especially for food and tents/pandal
 - f. Door to door visit: At least 100 farming families
 - g. Awareness and miking: 5 project habitations and adjacent village
 - h. Invitation to local officials: At least 10 members including Govt.

- i. Follow up action plan for implementation: Emerged from CSF
3. It is mandatory to follow the guideline of the government regarding COVID-19 during the Community Seed Fair (CSF)
- Maintaining social distancing during community mobilization and CSF.
 - Wearing mask is must by the farmers/participants, volunteers, coordinator, officials etc. Planned to provide mask and sanitizers to all participants.
 - There will not be more than 5 persons in the queue or any other discussion / gathering or food serving. Volunteers will maintain all these.
 - All participants will wash their hands thoroughly with soap-water and sanitizer and enter the ground of fair campus. Volunteers will pour sanitizer into their hands in front of main entrance and monitor the whole process.
 - Will display the slogan as a part of IEC (Information, education and communication) materials to fight against COVID-19.
4. State coordinator invited the the higher official of agriculture department, farm manager, scientist from Agriculture University and KVK, PRI members etc. for ensuring their participation in the fair.
5. The project team prepared a list of participants with their signature for reporting purpose.

Committees and Participation:

There were around 65 farmers including 48 women from project location and adjacent villages. The following table shows the active participation community leaders to make the community fair successful.

Sl.	Activities (Number of responsible persons)	Name of the committee-members	Contact Number
1.	Registration (2)	1 sangita soren	6203519425
		2 sorav kumar	"
2.	Logistic team (4)	1Anil marandi	
		2;Dinesh marandi	"
		3; amir soren	"
		4, babulal soren	"
3.	Decoration committee (3)	1 bimlesh kumar	"
		2 pradip yadav	"
		3 manish kumar	"
4.	Cultural committee (10)	1; makun hembrom	"
		2; sarita hembrom	9905511850
		3,sadmuni murmu	6207389554
		4 ;rani murmur	8083590455
		5anita soren	"
		6;phulmuni marandi	7858089617
		7;phuliya devi	"
		8; lilmuni marandi	"

		9;barki soren	6299871464
		10;sukurmuni marandi	9955096922
			"
5	Stall response video (1)	Lakshman kumar,kumar diwakar	9199996833
6	Stall response from fill-up	UPENDRA KUMAR RAM	6206460006
5.	Face book live (2)	Sudhansu kumar Chandan kumar	9031934146 8709164281
6.	Exit interview video (1)	Anurag kumar	7903207289
7.	Media / news paper publication (2)	R.k .jha	7004393743
8.	Overall monitoring (1)	Primal kumar singh(KVK)	9852455918
9.	Overall supervision (1)	Subhash chand dueby	7319853175

4. IMAGES/Photographs:

Fair Outcomes and Impacts:

The following shows the immediate outcome of this event

Seed Diversity in fair:

SL	Diversified seeds	Number varieties	of	Stalls No (best stall)
1	Urad	1		03and 17
2	Mustard black	4		
3	Masoor	2		
4	Til / Niger	1		
5	Mustard yelloe	3		
6	Tishi	1		
7	Khesari	0		
8	Arhar	2		
9	Maize	4		
10	Paddy	4		
11	Peas	1		
12	Lotni	1		
13	Ragi	1		
14	White til	1		
15	Black til	1		
16	Kudrum red	1		
17	Kudrum	1		
18	Moong	3		
19	Ghaghra	2		
		Total=34 (verity)		

Seed Distribution in fair

- Almost **35 farmers received different kinds of seeds (½ kg to 1kg) from the project**. The farmers and other stakeholders appreciated this initiative.

Women participation

- There were more than 110 farmers participated including **53 women farmers** in the fair and they realized the important of seeds and benefits of pulse cultivation as well.

Stakeholders

- The officials and delegates from govt. department, KVK, Jivika (implimentated by Bihar government).This fair built the relationship among the project team,

farming community and service providers. The following table shows the involvement of different stakeholders in the community seeds fair towards promotion of pulse and seeds.

S.No.	Name of the stakeholders	Address
1	Primal kumar singh	Kvk(deoghar)
2	Sona besra	Gram pradhan
3	Subhashchandra dubey	L.V.S(JAMUI)
4	Sukurmuni	Givika didi ,bihar

Awarded two stalls for biodiversity

- Two best stalls are awarded (Rs. 500/- each) by the project due to diversified seeds displayed and good gathering of farmers. **Stall No. 03 And 17.**

Awarded women in cultural programme

- There were games and cultural events for the participants to mobilize the farming community. Ten (10) women were awarded (Rs. 200/- each) for active participation in the cultural events. **The following table shows the list of those women.**

	Name,	phone	Award amount
1	Makun hembrom	“	200
2	Sarita hembrom	9905511850	200
3	Sadmuni murmu	6207389554	200
4	Rani murmur	8083590455	200
5	Anita soren	“	200
6	Phulmuni marandi	7858089617	200
7	Phuliya devi	“	200
8	Lilmuni marandi	“	200
9	Barki soren	6299871464	200
10	Sukurmuni marandi	9955096922	200

Way forward

- Linkage and convergence created through community seeds fair. The farmers are quite empowered towards pulse cultivation and farmers are planning to cultivate pulses and oil seeds in this winter.
- This seeds fair provided opportunity to the project team to scaling out the pulse cultivation in rice fallow area of different district.

Seed Biodiversity in Fair 2022:

Seed displayed in fair 2022

Stall No, Name of Farmers with Address	Crop/Seed displayed	Main crop, Millets, Pulses, Vegetables, Oil	Varieties /Local name	Local (L) / Improved (I)	Major, Neglected, Rare, Wild
Stall no 21, name ,majhali murmur,vill,koyadah	Paddy	Main crop	I	I	Major
	Rice	Main crop	Sorna	I	Major
	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Black musted	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	bazra	millets	L	L	neglected
Stall no 20, Name,soni tudu,vill tulsitar	Maize	Millets	L	L	Major
	Paddy	Main crop	6464	H	Major
	Chana	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Pumpkin	Vegetables	L	L	Neglected
	papaya	frutes	L	L	neglected

Stall no 19 , name rani hembrem , vill tulsitar	mung	pulses	L	L	major
	mazie	milletts	L	L	major
	rage	milletts	L	L	negleted
	masoor	pulses	L	L	negleted
	kulthi	pulses	L	L	major
Stall no 18 , name sangita hembrem, vill- koyadah	paddy	Main crop	775	haybret	major
	munge	pulses	L	L	major
	Red kudrum	oil	L	L	negleted
	Arhar	pulses	L	L	major
	Paddy	Main crop	I	I	major
	maize	milletts	L	L	major
Stall no 17 , name makun hembrem , vill- tulsitar	paddy	Main crop	6464	H	major
	maize	milletts	L (red)	L	major
	bazara	milletts	L	L	negleted
	kulthi	pulses	L	L	negleted
	rage	milletts	L	L	negleted
	Musted,yellow	oil	L	I	major
	Rage2	milletts	L	L	negleted
Stall no,16 name srita hembrem, vill- tulsitar	chana	pulses	L	L	negleted
	paddy	Main crop	I	I	major

	maize	milletts	L	L	major
	Musted yellow	oil	I	I	major
	Musted black	oil	I	I	major
	ghanhra	pulses	L	L	major
Stall no,15 name nunya murmu vill-magansar	paddy	maincrop	I	I	major
	arahar	pulses	L	L	major
	rage	milletts	L	L	negleted
	shim	vegitebal	L	L	major
	chanasag	vegitebal	L	L	negleted
	mazie	milletts	L	L	major
Stall no,14 name babita soren, vill-magensar	paddy	Main crop	I	I	Major
	chana	pulses	L	L	negleted
	tesi	oil	L	L	negleted
	Paddy sorna	Main crop	L	L	Major
	rage	milletts	L	L	negleted
	mazie	milletts	L	L	major
Stall no,13 name priya marendi vill-mangnasar	Paddy	Main crop	I	I	Major
	Munge	pulses	L	L	negleted
	chana	pulses	L	L	negleted
	kulthi	pulses	L	L	major
	nizer	oil	I	I	negleted

	Musted yellow	Oil	I	I	negleted
Stall no 12 , name sunita kisku ,vill-manganasar	paddy	Main crop	775	I	major
	munge	pulses	L	L	negleted
	ghangra	pulses	L	L	negleted
	mazie	milletts	L	L	major
	kulthi	pulses	L	L	major
Stall no 11 name santi marandi, vill-bhalsuviya	paddy	maincrop	lalath	I	major
	mazie	milletts	L	L	major
	arhar	pulses	I	L	major
	chana	pulses	I	L	negleted
	mazie	milletts	L	L	major
Stall no10, name manju besra, vill-koayade	mazie	milletts	L	L	major
	paddy	maincrop	I	I	major
	kulthi	pulses	L	L	major
	Musted yellow	oil	L	L	negleted
	kuduram	oil	L	L	major
Stall no ,9 name ,sarita murmur,vill,koyadah	Paddy	Main crop	I(saktiman)	I	Major
	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Neglegcted
	Yellow musted	Oil	L	L	Neglected

	White kudrum	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	Till black	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	Maize desi	milltes	L	L	major
Stall no 8,name,lalita kisku vill,tulsitar	Paddy	Main crop	teg	H	Major
	Chana	Pulses	Haat	I	neglected
	Musted yellow	Oil	haat	I	Major
	Lotni	Oil	L	L	neglected
	Ragi	Milltes	L	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	L	L	neglected
	Bazra	milletes	L	L	neglected
Stall no ,7 name anita soren vill,koyadah	Paddy	Main crop	I(sigham)	I	Major
	Chana	Pulses	Haat	I	Neglected
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Masoor	Pulses	Haat	I	Neglected
	Tisi	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	maize	milletes	L	L	major
Stall no 6,name,sunita soren,,vill,koyadah	Chana	Pulses	Haat	I	Neglected
	Moong	Pulses	Haat	I	Major
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Maize	Milletes	L	L	Major

	Paddy	Main crop	I sorna	I	Major
	Tisi	oil	L	L	neglected
Stall no5,name,chhotki marandi,koyadah	Maize	Millets	Desi white	L	Major
	Chana	Pulses	Haat	I	Neglected
	Masoor	Pulses	Haat	I	Neglected
	Paddy	Main crop	Lalat	I	Major
	kudrum	oil	desi	L	neglected
Stall no 4,name ,barki marandi,tulsitar	Maize	Millets	l	L	Major
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Tisi	Oil	L	L	neglected
	Paddy	Main crop	gorav	h	Major
	paddy	major	mahan	i	major
Stall no ,3 name ,hopan marandi,vill,tulsitar	Paddy	Main crop	Lalat	I	Major
	Urad	Pulses	Haat	I	Neglected
	Tisi	Oil	Desi	L	Neglected
	Kudrum	Oil	Desi	L	Neglected
	Papaya	Frutes	Desi	L	Neglected
	Ragi	millets	Desi	L	Neglected
	maize	milets	desi	L	major

Stall no. 2 name subodhi soren vill,tulsitar	Maize	Millets	L	L	Major
	Paddy	Main crop	Lalat	I	Major
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Chana	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	tisi	oil	L	L	neglected
Stall no 1 name lakshman kumar vill,dudhaniya	Bazra	Millets	L	L	Neglected
	Maize	Millets	L	L	Major
	Paddy	Main crop	I	I	Major
	Ragi	Millets	I	I	Neglected
	Maize	Millets	L	L	Major
	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Major
	chana	pulses	L	L	neglected
